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From Struggle to Strength: Understanding Resilience Through the Eyes of At-Risk High School Students

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study was to assist teachers in understanding the importance of fostering resilience among students facing adversity. Additionally, the study aimed to capture the perceptions of at-risk high school students regarding resilience-building. A descriptive research design employing a qualitative approach and multiple-case study methodology was utilized. The researcher explored the resilience perceptions of at-risk students from six selected public high schools in the District of Dinalupihan. Semi-structured interviews yielded findings that were categorized into five main themes with corresponding subthemes: (1) Challenges (family, school, and peers); (2) Coping (being knowledgeable, maintaining a positive attitude, lifestyle changes, support systems, and a healthy spiritual life); (3) Health (personal self-esteem and lifestyle, mental, emotional, and spiritual well-being); (4) Connection (companionship, self-esteem, information, and instrumental support); and (5) Aspirations (finishing school, helping parents, starting a business, and securing a good job). Key findings suggest that programs, projects, and interventions should be implemented to provide at-risk students with protective factors, such as academic support, to foster resilience and healthy development. Overall, the qualitative findings on risk, protection, and resilience, as perceived by the respondents, offer valuable insights that are often not captured in quantitative studies.

Keywords: *students at-risk, resilience, perception*

Introduction

Programs and practices that build resilience are particularly effective in improving the academic performance of low-achieving students. According to Banaag (1997), resilience involves adapting well in the face of adversity, trauma, tragedy, threats, or significant stress. It is the capacity to withstand, recover, and even grow from negative experiences, as childhood adversity can have potentially devastating consequences.

Responses to adversity vary, indicating that not everyone is capable of resilience or has a supportive environment that fosters it. Banaag suggests that what fosters resilience in one situation may not do so in another. The American Psychological Association (2013) notes that resilience is not an inherent trait but involves behaviors, thoughts, and actions that can be learned and developed, emphasizing that resilience is a process.

Schools are increasingly recognizing the importance of students' social and emotional well-being and a supportive school climate in promoting positive academic and behavioral outcomes. In the Philippines, teachers face the reality of at-risk youth struggling with academic challenges due to biological, psychological, and social factors.

Childhood is often idealized as a carefree time, but many children face emotional distress and traumas. They must deal with issues ranging from adapting to a new classroom to bullying or abuse at home, compounded by the uncertainties of growing up. The ability to thrive despite these challenges comes from resilience skills.

Adversities such as exposure to violence and conflict, drug use, peer pressure, low academic performance, street life, parental separation, and disabilities are common among children and adolescents. While some may succumb to these challenges, others demonstrate resilience, showing an ability to protect and restore their mental health independently. These individuals possess a stock of strength that allows them to bounce back from difficulties.

Luthar et al. (2000) point out that existing quantitative findings on vulnerability and resilience can be misleading, as they are often shaped by the risk and protective factors and outcomes included in a given model. The construct of resilience can be arbitrary and elusive, as youth may demonstrate resilience in one domain but not in another, making it challenging to capture such patterns in a single quantitative study. The inability of quantitative methodology to account for specific cultural and contextual factors is a major limitation.

In the Philippines, there is a scarcity of qualitative research on resilience. Evidence shows a rising number of bullying cases, high dropout rates, and students not completing secondary education. This study aims to complement existing quantitative data and provide references for future researchers.

Qualitative methodology adds depth and contextual relevance to current risk and resilience frameworks. The insights gained from adolescents' perspectives are crucial. The researcher believes that qualitative research on risk and resilience will provide a rich understanding of relevant factors in the participants' lives. Qualitative data collected in the study will help identify limitations in the hypothesized models and inform the development of intervention programs to promote resilience and reduce risk among adolescents.

Research Questions

The general problem of the study is to establish the perceptions of at-risk high school students on building resilience. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. grade level, and
 - 1.4. academic grades?
2. How may the high school students be categorized as young at risk?
3. How may the selected young at-risk high school students perceive resilience?
4. Based on the findings, what symbolic representation may be proposed?

Methodology

The study employed a qualitative design to understand the resilience perceptions of at-risk students. Ten participants were drawn from the 210 students who attended remedial classes in six schools in the District of Dinalupihan. The At-Risk Student Qualification Checklist was used to identify the participants: two females (20%) and eight males (80%) aged thirteen to eighteen. Parental consent was obtained through the school's adviser or guidance counselor, and in some cases, letter requests were sent home with the identified students. Both participants and their parents or guardians were oriented to the research purpose and informed that participation was voluntary.

Furthermore, the At-Risk Student Qualification Checklist was employed to identify cases based on pre-identified criteria or rubrics. The interview guide was used to gather interview data from the ten participants, utilizing the interview validation rubric. Initially designed to support the development of the Child and Youth Resilience Measure (CYRM), this guide has been employed in other studies by the RRC with at-risk youth globally to understand resilience processes across cultures and contexts better. The core of the interview schedule consists of nine "catalyst" questions developed collaboratively by an international research team. These questions were adapted and translated into Filipino to ensure comprehension and ease of response. The instrument was validated by a licensed psychologist, Filipino Master Teachers, and English Master Teachers, alongside the researcher's adviser and principal.

Meanwhile, open coding, as suggested by Give (2008), was used to identify and code themes from the interview data. This process involved labeling concepts and defining categories based on their properties and dimensions. During open coding, the collected data were divided into segments and scrutinized for commonalities reflecting categories or themes. Content analysis was then used to examine first-level concepts (master headings) and second-level categories (subheadings) based on theories of risk and resilience. Distinct concepts or themes were highlighted with different colors, transferred into a brief outline, and subsequently into a data table. A second round of analysis was conducted to ensure a deeper alignment with the youth voices. An expert reviewed the final themes and categories to promote validity.

Moreover, upon approval of the thesis proposal, a letter request was submitted to the school division superintendent to seek permission to conduct the interviews. The data collection process was detailed in the permit to prevent any issues during the research. Results and findings were shared with the Department of Education, the participating schools, and the student participants.

Results and Discussion

The general problem of this study is to establish the perceptions of at-risk high school students on building resilience using qualitative analysis. For clarity, this section is subdivided into four parts corresponding to the research questions. Part 1 describes the profile of the at-risk high school students in terms of age, grade level, and academic grades in English, Mathematics, Science, and Filipino. Part 2 categorizes the respondents as at-risk students based on the At-Risk Students Qualification Checklist criteria. Part 3A presents the results of the qualitative coding analysis of the interview data gathered using the Interview Guide. Part 3B establishes the insights drawn from the Narrative Case Stories of the participants. Part 4 presents the proposed symbolic representations based on the findings.

Profile of the Participants

Table 1 shows the profile of the participants in terms of age.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Participants by Age*

Respondents	Age					
	13	14	15	16	17	18
Student A						1
Student B					1	
Student C			1			
Student D					1	
Student E						1
Student F			1			
Student G	1					

Student H	1					
Student I						1
Student J	1					
f	2	0	3	0	2	3
%	20.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	20.00	30.00

The table presents the profile of the participants according to age. Three (3), or 30% of the participants were 18 years old; three (3), or 30%, were 15 years old; two (2), or 20%, were 17 years old, and two (2), or 20% also were 13 years old. Half of them are more than sixteen (16) years old who are considered over-aged in junior high school. They are supposed to be in senior high school already.

These data are parallel with the findings of Child Hope Asia Philippines, Inc., which stated that at-risk street children comprise about 1-3% of the children and youth population of the major cities in the Philippines. Metro Manila and the National Capital Region (NCR) have an estimated 30,000 children on the streets. In contrast, nationwide, some 250,000 street children are believed to be plying the streets of major urban centers. From available studies, most are boys aged 7 to 16 years. About 75% of them still return home to families after working or begging on the streets

Table 2 shows the profile of the participants according to grade level.

Table 2. Distribution of the Participants by Grade Level

Respondents	Grade Level			
	7	8	9	10
Student A				1
Student B				1
Student C			1	
Student D				1
Student E			1	
Student F	1			
Student G		1		
Student H	1			
Student I			1	
Student J			1	
f	2	1	4	3
%	20.00	10.00	40.00	30.00

Four (4) or 40% of the participants are Grade 9 students, three (3) or 30% are Grade 10, two (2) or 20% are Grade 7 and one (1) or 10% is a Grade 8 student. These data show that majority of the respondents belong to an older age-bracket.

Grade 9 and Grade 10 are considered difficult levels in the junior high school. It is perceived to be crucial and demanding in terms of academic demands. Once a secondary student did not master the competencies in Grade 7 and Grade 8 since it is intertwined to next year level, he will struggle in later part of his schooling in the secondary level.

The K to 12 Basic Education came in 2011. Republic Act No. 10533, otherwise known as the “Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2011”, Rule 2. Curriculum, Section 10.2.g. Standards and Principles, “The curriculum shall use the spiral progression approach to ensure mastery of knowledge and skills after each level”. Enclosure No. 1 to Department of Health (DepEd) Order No. 31, s 2012 is the “Implementing Guidelines of Grades 1 to 10 to Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum”, which states that “the overall design of Grades 1 to 10 curriculum follows the spiral approach across subjects by building on the same concepts developed in increasing complexity and sophistication starting from grade school. The spiral progression of topics in each subjects reveals how lessons are intertwined in every year level meaning there is a continuity of lessons in each subjects in all grade levels. In the study conducted by Samala (2018) about the Spiral Progression, majority of the students stated that going back to their lessons in the past years before the start of the new lesson in their current grade level made them understand the latter. On the other hand, the students who were able to understand the complex lessons by connecting their previous lessons to the new ones. Familiarity of the lessons was gained by having the same concepts in a specific area in all grade levels attributed to the nature of spiral progression.

Table 3 shows the profile of the participants according to academic grades in English, Mathematics, Filipino and Science.

Table 3. Distribution of the Participants Academic Grade

Respondents	Subjects				Average
	English	Mathematics	Filipino	Science	
Student A	68	74	-	-	N/A
Student B	75	72	74	73	73.5
Student C	72	71	75	73	72.75
Student D	72	73	75	73	73.25
Student E	71	72	73	72	72
Student F	72	75	75	72	73.5
Student G	72	76	76	74	74.5

Student H	76	75	75	72	74.5
Student I	75	75	85	75	77.5
Student J	-	75	-	73	N/A
Total	653	738	608	657	288.06
Mean	72.56	73.8	76	73	72.01
Descriptor	Did Not Meet Expectations	Did Not Meet Expectations	Fairly Satisfactory	Did Not Meet Expectations	Did Not Meet Expectations
Remarks	Failed	Failed	Passed	Failed	Failed

Student A and Student J have no grades in two subjects. This means that they cannot complete the requirements set by these subjects due to some reasons. English has the lowest mean which is 72.56, followed by Science with a mean of 73.00, and Mathematics got 73.8, all of which are considered failed, or “did not meet expectations”. Filipino has the only passing rate of 76.00, described as “fairly satisfactory.”

In terms of the individual average of the participants, only Student I has a passing general average of 77.5. The rest of the other participants have a failed general average in terms of the four identified academic subjects. The findings are consistent with Senobio, M. (2015) in his article Why English is so very hard to teach and learn, is that “the first, and the most crucial, reason for the student’s bad English is their negative attitude today toward the language.”

Table 5 also shows that the participants have very little chances of passing their subjects in school. According to Hernandez (2011), children who experience academic problems early in life are at risk to have or encounters problem later in life. For example, children who cannot read proficiently by the third grade are four times less likely to graduate from high school on time than other youth.

Part 2. Categories of the Participants as At-risk Students

Using the At-risk Student Qualification Checklist, the researcher identified the cases of the ten (10) participants as to how severe is the case on developing resilience and minimizing the risks.

Table 4 shows the categories of the participants as at-risk students.

Table 4. Categories of the Participants as At-Risk Students (Multiple Response)

A	Criteria	f	%
1	Has repeated one (1) grade level.	7	70
2	Has absenteeism that is greater than ten (10%) percent during the first semester of the current school year.	9	90
3	Had incurred absenteeism which was more than 20% of the required number of class days in a school year.	8	80
4	Has back subject/s from the previous school years.	3	30
5	Has failed one (1) or more academic subjects this school year.	3	30
6	Is classified as a non-reader.	1	10
B	Criteria	f	%
1	Has substance abusive behavior.	5	50
2	Is pregnant or a parent.	2	20
3	Is an emancipated youth.	0	0
4	Is a previous dropout.	4	40
5	Has serious personal, emotional, or medical problem.	3	30
6	Is a court or agency referral.	0	0
7	Recommended by another school/district as determined by locally developed criteria for disruptive student behavior.	0	0

It can be gleaned from table 4 that the highest of all the cases is absenteeism: 1.) nine (9) or 90% had absenteeism that is greater than ten (10%) percent during the first semester of the current school year; 2.) eight (8) or 80% had incurred absenteeism which was more than 20% of the required number of class days in a school year; and seven (7) or 70% had repeated one (1) grade level. Consistent with these findings is that of Maguin and Loeber (1996), who discussed that academic failure and lack of commitment to school are important risk factors for child and adolescent behavior problems.

Five (5) out of 10 or 50% of the respondents are found to have substance abusive behavior. Family risk factors are among the strongest and most consistent risk factors for child and adolescent problem behavior. According to Barton (2006), Frey et al. (2011) and Herrenkohl et al. (2000), family management problems – defined generally by inconsistent parental supervision, monitoring and discipline – are generally associated with many child and adolescent problem behaviors.

Moreover, four (4) or 40% of the participants were previous dropouts. Consistent with this is that of Archambault et al. (2009) who revealed in his study that low school engagement, an indicator of a student’s involvement in classroom and extra-curricular activities, is associated with school dropout and other problem behaviors.

Three (3) cases or 30% of the participants had back subjects from previous school years, had failed one or more academic grade/s this

school year, and had a serious personal, emotional or medical problem. Two (2) cases or 20% were identified as pregnant or a parent and one (1) respondent was classified as a non-reader.

In terms of the participants' dealing with school and peers, having friends who participate in antisocial behavior is one of the strongest and most consistent risk factors for problem behavior (Fergusson & Horwood 2003; Reinherz et al. 2000). Other school-level risks include experiences of discrimination from peers and teachers and victimization by peers (Glew et al. 2005; Nansel et al., 2004; Rosenbloom & Way 2004). In contrast, school-level protective factors include commitment to learning, involvement with positive peers, and healthy bonds with teachers and other adults (Frey et al. 2011).

Interviews were transcribed and analyzed using constant comparative analytic methods (Boeiji 2002). The process involved: coding within a single transcript; comparison of codes between transcripts to develop categories; analysis of how and if each category is connected in order to develop new categories, combine existing categories, and delete others.

The initial phase of analysis used content analysis to examine major categories of responses based on the theories of risk and resilience. Quotes were first categorized according to content the identified domains such as peer group, family, neighborhood, etc. The contexts and relationships within these quotes were then examined again in reference to fear of gangs, school problems, supportive parents, trusted friends etc. using color codes.

The first round of analysis resulted in eight (8) initial categories that were tentatively labeled: resources; challenges; coping; advice to other youth; aspirations; self-concept; relationships; and health. However, these were reduced to five (5) during the second round of analysis using the constant comparison method (Boeije, 2002). The category resources were deleted because this can be attributed and connected to the other categories such as challenges depending on what kind of resource is lacking. Advice to other youth was also merged with aspirations. Self-concept and relationships were deleted and merged using a new category called connection. This process resulted in the formulation of five themes and their subthemes to show the real meaning of the transcripts being transcribed by the researcher.

Part 3. Qualitative Result

Study results are presented into five major themes with their corresponding subthemes:

Challenges

This theme describes participants' difficult or negative experiences. This theme includes quotes that express respondents' views of the difficult and negative experiences in their lives. For instance, one respondent related why he was involved in bad influences of friends. It contains three sub-themes namely: family, school and peers. Three participants expressed the challenges of having difficult family relationships. Two (2) participants reported on-going challenges in going to school every day. Some participants noted personal challenges associated with missing an absent family member. Basically, students who encounter more challenges in their families, schools, and peers are more prone to risks and have difficulties developing resilience.

Coping

When participants described challenges, they were probed to explain how they managed these situations. Quotes that included content in which participants explained how they responded to challenges make up the theme of coping. The subthemes of being knowledgeable, being positive, lifestyle change, support system and healthy spiritual life describe the range of coping mechanisms that were used by the respondents to confront challenges. These categories of coping refer to the descriptions of action taken in response to a challenge.

The next quotes describe "coping by being knowledgeable" of the participants as a response to their challenges: "...Yung pong mga lesson na tinuturo ng mga teacher dahil ito po ay magagamit ko pag ako ay nakapagtrabaho na. Dapat ko din pong malaman na dapat magtyaga at maging masipag para makatapos at ng makatulong kay nanay..."; "...Maging matapang at lumaban kung kinakailangan para hindi ka inaapi. Matapos po ng pag-aaral para magkaroon ng magandang buhay pagdating ng araw..."

"Coping by being positive" refers to quotes that described youth applying an internal mental process of optimism for figuring out responses to challenges. One participant explained how he responded to the challenge of difficult academic work.

"Coping by changing the lifestyle" refers to looking for activities that will divert their attention in order to cope. Five (5) or 50% of the participants go with their friends (barkada) in times of challenges or troubles. To them, they feel secured and loved by their peers.

"Coping by looking for a support system" means looking for people who can give strong support in order to face the challenges. Two (2) participants said that they run to their families to be able to cope with challenges.

Coping, as perceived by the participants, represents unlikely behavior when running to their peers as the source of strength. This implies that they can find the needed support from friends who become their immediate confidante and whom they believe can understand their situation. Further, the physical presence of peers became evident that respondents can feel family-like atmosphere every time that they are with their friends or adults, specifically people who can serve as their parents is needed in order to strengthen their coping in terms

of having knowledge, optimism, support system and healthy spiritual life, thereby acquiring more resilience as they grow.

Health

The health theme includes all quotes in which youth expressed something that they perceived to be positive or healthy, either directly experienced in their lives, or known to exist in their communities. Health quotes represent a range of domains of the social ecology and subthemes were identified accordingly as personal esteem and lifestyle, mental, emotional and spiritual. Nine (9) or 90% of the participants viewed 'health' as a personal esteem. One (1) participant talked about 'health' as being positive about healthy family. In order to keep mentally, physically, emotionally and spiritually healthy, ten (10) participants identified the types of food to eat and the lifestyle that they need to follow. In terms of mental health, four (4) participants said that smoking or using drugs should be avoided. In terms of emotional health, three (3) participants said that they should not deal with love or relationships seriously. Most of the participants emphasized the importance of praying in order to make them spiritually healthy.

Similar to the relationship between risk factors and the challenges theme, the health theme is closely connected to common protective factors. There were a range of positive experiences and influences within the cultural context of growing up that were described by the youth. All of these experiences can be connected conceptually to protective factors found in the empirical literature. However, similar to risk, youth perspectives again add important further insight about what they value, what they believe these factors are protecting them from, and purposes and benefits they find in the efforts of others.

The participants basically viewed health as a very important factor in order to move forward despite the challenges. They felt blessed despite of the problems that they encounter. Further, they understand the importance of having a healthy community and neighborhood. They felt that they are still fortunate to have the chance to attend school, have a healthy and not sickly family members, and a healthy body themselves. All these are connected to having a good coping mechanism in order to develop self-resilience.

The data reveal a range of ways in which interpersonal relationships contribute important positive functions in the lives of youth while growing up in their community. The theme connection delineates the types of support the youth described.

Connection

The theme connection contains all descriptions of supportive interpersonal relationships. All participants mentioned the importance of connections or relationships in their lives.

Four subthemes emerged which describe the range of types of positive relationships that the youth described. The 4 types of childhood support: companionship, esteem, information, and instrumental by Tietjen (1989) was used by the researcher in labeling the quotes.

Eight (8) or 80% of the participants said that they never knew of personalities or people who were able to succeed in their community amidst the challenges that they faced. According to them, they only saw or watched those cases on television. On the other hand, two (2) participants said that their families are their source of companionship in order to grow up well in the community despite the many challenges.

Another way of labeling the quotes is to identify the ways in which the respondents benefited from the relationships they mentioned. Also quotes which reflect the aspect of relationship that promotes a sense of belonging were categorized in this theme. These quotes exemplify the strong connections and bonds of the respondents with the people they consider as their source of support so that they can conceptualize what they want to be like when they grow up.

These few people whom they consider very precious to them make a strong bond of connection that they believe will support them all throughout their journey in life. They believed that the connections that they have are their only hope to overcome and cope with the challenges, thereby making them more resilient in the process.

Aspirations

The fifth theme, aspirations, represents quotes from participants that contain content about what they wanted to do in the future, who they wanted to be like when they grow up, and what they are doing already that will help them reach their goals. Based on the responses, the five (5) sub-themes were developed: finish school; help the parents; have a business and have a good job.

Five (5) participants said the finishing the school is the way to reach their goals. Although they did not mention specific role models like becoming a policeman or a teacher, they expressed their belief that education can greatly help them to cope. Expressions of aspirations provide clues about the resilience young people have developed by this particular moment in time. The extent of their ability to conceptualize roles they might fulfill, the qualities of role models they intend to be like, and the personal attributes that they believe they possess that will help them attain success are likely to be important ingredients for striving and perseverance. In case of the ten (10) respondents, they could hardly identify their role models that they intend to be like. Their answers were not concrete and realistic and were just manifestations of the "supposedly good behaviors" that they felt they like to portray. Young people with such attitudes may also have a limited ability to identify which characteristics they possess that will help them accomplish what they want or expect in life.

These cases of having short of aspirations and ambitions may lead to life's failure, most likely. Their inability to concretize their own

'wants' and 'needs' is seemingly a manifestation of not having a role model to emulate. Further, the lack of ideas and the inability to create their aspirations might lead to more risks. In this case, paramount attention should be given to these respondents in terms of providing close monitoring and supervision, guidance, and counseling.

Symbolic Representations Based on the Findings

The following symbolic representation is proposed by the researcher as a perfect fit for the findings of this study:

The figure shows the significant connection of challenges, coping up, health, aspiration, and connection to resiliency. To some, resiliency comes naturally in facing different struggles in life, but to others it requires a lot of effort and perseverance to build their resiliency. It is a trait considered to bring positivity in every challenge one may encounter. One may say it is an ability to stand taller after being knocked down by a problem.

Resiliency is connected to different aspect. One of these aspects that affect the resiliency of the child is his ability to cope up with different challenges. According to Positive Psychology article (2020), coping up is like bouncing back with the disappointments, defeats, and failures that we face. Coping up is fighting back or accepting what is being thrown to you instead of letting things brings you down. This coping up skill is very essential for an individual to build a good resiliency.

Coping up with challenges in life is never easy if an individual lacks in good health. If we are talking about resiliency then good health may not only be seen in the physical aspect of an individual. A good holistic health including mental health is required. If you have the will to survive and the ability to see the brighter things in life this can lead to building your shield or your resiliency.

Connection also plays a great role in improving once resiliency. If an individual have a good support system such as family or friends, it will become easier for them to cope up with problems. An individual may feel like giving up or feel like losing up with life if he got no one to turn to when problem arises. The connection with your loved once may ignite aspiration to live a better and a happy life despite the challenges. This aspiration may result to an individual who is resilient or someone who can withstand or recover quickly from a very difficult situation.

Therefore, these aspects are all interrelated with one another. To cope up properly with a disastrous event in life, one must be physically and mentally healthy. A person's mental health is greatly affected by the connections he has or the people who surrounds him. Aspiration may be the reason why a person strives better after every problem in life. In short, these aspects play a significant role in building a resilient person.

Conclusions

This study gathered youth's voices and perspectives about their lived experiences of risk, protection, and resilience in the context of the public school system where they attend education. The purpose of this study was to use findings that are accessible to teachers, parents, and schools to enable them to make interventions based on risk and resilience perspectives. Key findings suggest that programs, projects and interventions should be provided to at-risk students in order to ensure the provision of protective factors like academic support to achieve resilient behavior and healthy development. In sum, the qualitative findings on the depiction of risk, protection, and resilience, as viewed by the participants, provide relevant information that is not often conveyed in quantitative investigations. Lastly, a closer examination of the lived experiences of at-risk youth in the study increases current understanding of how young people living in underprivileged environments tend to perceive the efforts of others to support their healthy development.

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